

There is no Tool to Development more Effective than the Empowerment of Women: A Socio-Literary Perspective brought to Limelight

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Abstract

There is no world and world development without women. The force and the power of the macrocosm largely dwell in women, untapped and realistic it is still vibrant yet lying idle among the society. The macrocosm as a large family has diversified systems, cultures, traditions, societal clans, best practices, life styles and governmental impacts on existing living form of mankind. Life and generations is sure not to exist without the rhythm of women; she is the heart string of the society and the macrocosm in complete unison. The world would turn barren and devoid of growth in absence of the power of women. The stately form a man exalts in the power of women. Social awareness on protection and establishment of such a power believed in every part of the world, which ever the country of existence. There have been multitudinous writer, authors, socialists and people of different walks of life who have put forward views and philosophies in women development and expressed angst on the atrocities leveled against women, taken to be the weaker sections of the society. This paper would highlight and bring to limelight the well being of women through some eminent writers/authors of the world. The perspectives through the expressions of female writers, a personal relevance of those writers and that has given impetus to the concept of womanhood and provide a solution in establishing equanimity to existence of a woman.

Keywords: Macrocosm, diversified, heartstring, establishment, multitudinous, eminent, equanimity.

“Kiki arrived at the river, fetched the water and was soon on her way home. She walked, the sunset behind her, a silhouette of an upright young woman with a clay pot on her head-the typical image of an African woman. For the first time the weight of the clay pot pressing down on her became a conscious reality, a force that she had to sustain against the laws of gravity. Just then it struck her vividly that African women are heavily loaded. On their heads they carry the heavy burdens of firewood and clay pots; in their hands they carry bags; on their backs they carry babies; and their front carries the load of man in procreation. Their hearts are heavily loaded with burdens of sorrow. All this is because their worth is measured in terms of the number of burdens they can carry. Even beasts have an easier task”.

The Status of women as from the past to the present is a depiction as in the passage above taken from the novel “What the Future Holds by Sarah Mkhonza of Swaziland. From the past observations and to a large extent in this present societal scenario, women are treated as less important in different walks of life. In varied societies of the world, the impact differs and women are generally banished from the public spheres of power and establishments. In spite of the alienation that the women face, they stand by as torch bearers of peace and dignity for their society. The eminent and unique roles that they play whereby, women hold the indispensable function of life-giver and peacekeeper uplifting the power to protect life.

Herein, the focus is brought to the expressionist writing of Kamala Das, The eminent English writer of India. Her vibrant realistic poetic outbursts were a passionate form of living of a woman. Her own life with trials and tribulations served as building blocks for her expression to the macrocosm. Nothing is untrue yet truthful rendition of the reality where women status, livelihood, gender bias, gender discrimination, patriarchal indulgences, consummate art, schizophrenia, anatomy, love, lust and sex are all dealt on a complete wholeness to focus the difficulties faced by women and the possibilities of segregating to be unique is realized in her writings

The literature of Kamala Das is a distinct, unique, and singularly famous component of Indian English Literature and by extension World Literature. It is a growing phenomenon. It cannot be ignored. Its relevance, significance and consequence cannot be gainsaid. It is committed to exploring the opportunities, inanities, the loyalties and above all the triumphs of women. It is highly motivating in character. It motivates the women to realize their twin strengths, which is that women alone can carry the universe within themselves and approximate the creative work in bringing into being new births, and secondly it is the women alone who can initiate man into right action. Moreover, it opens the eyes of the women to know who they are, where they are, what they are and what they are not capable of. In other words, it educates women to discover themselves, their inner strengths, and their limitations and think and act accordingly.

The literature of Das dismisses the notion that patriarchy is the established order, and that the male has already set himself as the human norm, the subject and referent to which the female is the “other” or alien. Whatever its origin, the function of the male’s sexual antipathy is to provide a means of control over a subordinate group and a rationale, which justifies the inferior station of those in a lower order “explaining” the oppression of their lives. Her contribution offers rich recommendations and guidelines to women the ways and means to empower themselves. In poignant language and style, she advocates to the women to go in for rich and quality higher education, and enter the competitive world and gain a position of status and achieve economic independence and thereby strike upward mobility and ultimately attain recognition.

There is the persistent and worldwide feeling that the biological and sexual functions of the women are impure. One detects evidence of the biological condition of the female being considered impure in literature and myth. The vent of menstruation, for instance, is a largely clandestine affair, and the psychological effect of the stigma attached has a great effect on the female ego. There is a large anthropological literature on menstrual taboo; the practice of isolating menstruating females in huts at the edge of the village occurs throughout the primitive world. Contemporary slang dominates menstruation as the curse. On this point Kate Millet makes a pointed observation, [Sexual Politics, 1972]

There is considerable evidence that such discomfort as women suffer during this period [period of menstruation] is often likely to be psychosomatic, rather than psychological, cultural rather than biological, in origin. That this also may be true to some extent of labor and delivery is attested to be the experiment with “painless childbirth”. Patriarchal circumstances and beliefs seem to have the effect of poisoning the female’s own sense of physical self until it often truly becomes the burden it is said to be. (p.73).

It ought to be stressed, that in the primitive period the terms of a wound, sometimes reasoning that she was visited by a bird or snake, and mutilated her into her present condition. Once she was wounded, now she bleeds. The female vagina is described in contemporary slang as a gash.

The Freudian description of the female genitals is in terms of a castrated condition. The uneasiness and disgust that the female genitals arouse in patriarchal societies is attested through religious, cultural, and literary prescription.

It ought to be noted that in all patriarchal societies the dominant male eats first or eats better food, and even before the male and female eat together, the male is served by the female. Yet again, all patriarchs enforce taboos against women touching ritual objects [those of war or religion] or food. It is because women are considered by their biological condition unclean. Therefore, the women are not permitted to eat with men. Women eat apart in many countries even at this point of time.

It is the female who endures the attendant bodily pains and mental anguish in defloration. It ought to be noted that in the houses of men, boys have such low status that they are often called the wives of their initiators, the term "wife" implying both inferiority and the status of sexual object. The derogation of female status in lesser males is a patriarchal trait. The psychoanalytic term for the generalized adolescent tone of the house culture of men is the "phallic state". Men consider themselves as the citadel of virility. Therefore, men enforce the most saliently power-centered characteristics of patriarchy. It is in such a context of patriarchy that Women Literature advocates to the women to take pride in the female sex, and shed their inferiority complexes, castration complex, and fear psychosis.

Moreover, the literature of Das educates the women to shed their submissive attitudes and approaches to life and emerge as women who have gained real empowerment to face any kind of challenge in life. It is helpful in guiding the perceptive women readers to discover their inherent strengths through self-definition and self-discovery. Above all, it champions the cause of the women in their struggle for intellectual, moral, spiritual, economic, social, and political survival, and for their empowerment and emergence as women capable of doing all that the male sex is capable of, if not better. In fact, it awakens in the hearts of all perceptive readers a stronger sense of justice and a more Christian-like humanity. In all these respects it has proved itself to be educative, instructive, and trend setting.

It ought to be stressed at this point that the contributions made by Das, the Indian-English, to the growth, development and phenomenal strength of Women Literature and by extension to World Literature is significant, relevant, and consequential. She cannot be dismissed as a second-class writer when compared with male writers. In this context, it ought to be stressed that women could not survive unless they generated some other than a female artist, can project the mind and heart of a woman fittingly, comprehensively, effectively, and accurately. A Hawthorne, a Hemingway, a Faulkner, a Mailer, a Doctorow, a Bellow, a Cummings, a James Joyce to quote a few could not express in their artistic products effectively the feelings, the sufferings, thoughts, and experiences of a woman. The range and spectrum of the realities of a female life lie beyond the purview of the male mind.

Moreover, the male artists never introduce the right kind of image of the woman, precisely because they have no understanding of the biological conditions and the mind workings of the woman. Hence, the need was felt for the emergence of women writers who alone could capture the feelings, thoughts, experiences, the plights and predicaments, hopes and aspirations, the failures and frustrations of the women. In fact the women artists alone could artistically and realistically deal with the denials, deprivations, degeneration, exploitation, and dehumanization experienced by the women at the hands of the male chauvinists. It is the female artists alone who could give

the right kind of direction to the women to empower themselves and rise and emerge as women of status and recognition. Therefore, there was an emergence of outstanding women writers all over the world, who were responsible for bringing out the distinct and unique variety of literature, termed as Women Literature. And the need for the emergence of female writers of repute and eminence has been fully fulfilled by women writers all over the world.

Das directs her constant attention and reveals her intention towards a refutation of the negative images of women imposed on women by the male writers. On the other hand, if the women tried to live by the standards set by the male chauvinists they would never be able to emerge as empowered women. They should not live by the female version of the pure, refined, gentle, protected and well provided for introduced and put into practice. Such a living is easy, but the women will be destroyed, frustrated and alienated for generations together in the male dominated world.

In the first phase of Literature of Das, there is the general refutation of the male dominated world's version of what a female should be. In other words there is the refutation of the general society's definition of women. It does not omit the complex existence of the woman when compared with that of man. Then there is the emphasis on the need for the women to be engaged in self-definition and self-discovery.

Incidentally, Das has introduced a re-vision of creativity and creative process. Her purpose sense or argumentation has a direct bearing on postmodern women. The inspirational role models projected as female protagonists in her works, are drawn from literary foremothers or feminist co-creators, women from her own life - - mothers, lovers, one or many sisters - - aspects of her own psyche. Moreover, she has refused to be the obedient mouthpiece of male authors and be governed by the male literary convention. Instead she has delved into what Adrienne Rich has called the cratered night of the female memory to touch the true matrix: the wisdom of mankind.

Das has been instrumental in arguing for femaleness with conviction, faith, and purpose. Advances in social theories and practices have differently affected her, and how these have transformed female psyche and female autonomy. She has successfully introduced feminist modernism. She has in large measure succeeded in resolving the contradictions, tensions and anxieties - - Angst - - and the stresses and strains - - Sturm-und-Drang experienced by women in the post satellite era.

Das argues convincingly and persuasively that only through sophisticated learning, training, and developing processes that a woman can empower herself. She should possess the highest quality education, be dynamic, pragmatic, progressive, assertive, and positive to experience empowerment. Only then, she could shed her inferiority and dependent complexes, and be economically independent and free. Das gives adequate expression to her female mind, which earn for her Oeuvres that admirable reach of perspectives as enunciated and interpreted by Austin Warren thus [Theory of Literature, 1949,]:

“We must rather adopt a view for which the term, Perspectivism, seems suitable. We must be able to refer a work of art to the values of its own time and of all the periods of subsequent to its own”.(p. 34)

Conclusively, we can adjunct the fact that women as the soulful form of divinity need the pristine living standards for the development of the world directly and to assure of good standard ethics and norms to sustain the creation. Well established and formative systems for the development of women should be adhered to break the bonds of inferiority, thereby to establish a uniform pattern of expression and acceptance of the world of women

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